

COMPARATIVE MORPHOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF HUMAN (*HOMO SAPIENS*) AND DOMESTIC GOAT (*CAPRA HIRCUS*) SCAPULAE

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ABSTRACT

The scapula is a key component of the mammalian pectoral girdle, and its morphology reflects adaptations to species-specific locomotor and functional demands. This study compared the morphology and morphometry of the scapula in humans (*Homo sapiens*) and domestic goats (*Capra hircus*), representing bipedal and quadrupedal locomotor strategies, respectively. Ten adult scapulae (five human and five goats) were ethically sourced and examined. Morphological characteristics were assessed from the anterior, posterior, and medial aspects, while morphometric parameters, including spine length, acromion dimensions, glenoid fossa radius, and coracoid process dimensions, were measured using digital calipers. Quantitative data were analysed using independent sample t-tests and expressed as mean \pm SEM. Marked morphological and morphometric differences were observed between the two species. The human scapula exhibited a well-developed acromion process (length: 5.0 ± 0.18 cm; width: 4.5 ± 0.30 cm) and a prominent coracoid process (length: 4.3 ± 0.15 cm), whereas the goat scapula displayed a reduced acromion, a rudimentary coracoid process associated with the supraglenoid tubercle complex, a distinct scapular neck, and a relatively deeper glenoid cavity. A suprascapular notch was observed in humans but not in the goat specimens examined. These findings suggest that human scapular morphology is associated with increased upper-limb mobility, whereas the goat scapula exhibits features consistent with stability and weight-bearing function during quadrupedal locomotion, highlighting the influence of locomotor adaptation on scapular structure.

Keyword: Human, goat, scapula, morphometric, shoulder girdle, comparative anatomy

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INTRODUCTION

The scapula is a key component of the pectoral girdle in mammals, functioning as the primary osseous link between the axial skeleton and the forelimb. Its morphology is closely associated with locomotor strategy, upper-limb function, and the mechanical demands imposed by posture and movement (Standing, 2021; Moore *et al.*, 2022). Across mammals, scapular shape variation reflects functional trade-offs between mobility, stability, and force transmission, making it a highly informative structure in comparative and evolutionary anatomy (Lieberman, 1997; Jacxsens *et al.*, 2020; Vermeulen *et al.*, 2023).

In humans (*Homo sapiens*), the evolution of habitual

bipedalism resulted in the functional liberation of the upper limb from locomotor duty. This transition was accompanied by substantial reorganisation of the shoulder girdle, including dorsal repositioning of the scapula, expansion of muscular attachment sites, and increased mobility at the glenohumeral joint (Standing, 2021; Laudicina and Cartmill, 2023). These modifications support a broad range of upper-limb movements required for manipulation, tool use, and fine motor control. The human scapula, therefore, reflects a structural configuration associated with enhanced mobility and neuromuscular control rather than weight-bearing function (Jacxsens *et al.*, 2020).

In contrast, the domestic goat (*Capra hircus*) is a quadrupedal ungulate whose forelimb is primarily

adapted for weight-bearing locomotion and energy-efficient terrestrial movement (Dyce *et al.*, 2023; König and Liebich, 2020). In such species, the scapula contributes significantly to load transmission and locomotor stability through its broad muscular surfaces and reinforced bony architecture. Compared with humans, ungulate scapulae typically exhibit reduced prominence of distal processes and increased structural emphasis on joint congruence and repetitive cyclical loading (Dyce *et al.*, 2023; Makungu and Merere, 2017).

Comparative anatomical studies have demonstrated that scapular morphology varies systematically with locomotor behaviour across mammals. Species engaged in manipulative or suspensory activities tend to exhibit increased scapular mobility and expanded muscular leverage structures, whereas cursorial and weight-bearing taxa display configurations that prioritise stability and efficient force transmission during locomotion (Vermeulen *et al.*, 2023; Kang *et al.*, 2023; Jacxsens *et al.*, 2020). However, despite growing interest in functional morphology, direct quantitative comparisons between the scapula of humans and domestic goats remain limited in the literature, particularly with respect to integrating morphometric data with detailed structural observations.

Given the functional divergence between bipedal primates and quadrupedal ungulates, a comparative assessment of scapular morphology provides an opportunity to better understand how skeletal architecture reflects locomotor demands (Lieberman, 1997; Laudicina and Cartmill, 2023; Vermeulen *et al.*, 2023; Jacxsens *et al.*, 2020). Such analyses also contribute baseline anatomical data relevant to evolutionary biology, veterinary anatomy, and musculoskeletal biomechanics (Makungu and Merere, 2017; Vermeulen *et al.*, 2023; Kang *et al.*, 2023).

Therefore, this study aimed to perform a detailed morphological and morphometric comparison of the scapulae of humans (*Homo sapiens*) and domestic goats (*Capra hircus*). It was hypothesised that significant interspecific differences would be observed in scapular dimensions and structural features, reflecting distinct adaptations to manipulative upper-limb function in humans and weight-bearing locomotion in goats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical Approval: Formal ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of the Department of Anatomy, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Specimen Selection: A total of ten dry, fully ossified scapulae consisting of five human (*Homo sapiens*) and five domestic goat (*Capra hircus*) specimens were selected for analysis. The inclusion criteria required that all specimens belong to skeletally mature adults and possess completely intact anatomical landmarks. Any scapulae demonstrating osteological deformities, pathological lesions, or post-mortem fractures were excluded to guarantee the accuracy of the morphometric data.

Source and Handling: All specimens were ethically sourced from the curated skeletal archives of the Department of Anatomy Museum, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University. Official academic authorization was granted by the designated legal custodian of the collection. Human specimens were strictly anonymized, and all handling procedures adhered to respectful, standardized osteological curation practices.

Morphological Evaluation: Comprehensive qualitative morphological evaluations were performed systematically on the posterior (lateral in quadrupeds), anterior (costal), and medial/articular surfaces of each scapula. Key anatomical features assessed included the acromion process, scapular spine, supraspinous/suprascapular fossa, infraspinous fossa, subscapular fossa, scapular neck, suprascapular notch, coracoid process, and the articular geometry of the glenoid cavity.

Morphometric Analysis and Statistical Framework: Anthropometric dimensions of defined scapular landmarks were measured using digital vernier calipers (Mitutoyo, Japan) calibrated to 0.01 mm precision. The quantified parameters included: Spine Length, Acromion Length, Acromion Width, Glenoid Fossa Radius Length, Coracoid Process Length, and Coracoid Process Width (measured at the base).

Statistical Analysis: To minimize intra-observer error, each measurement was obtained in triplicate and the mean value was recorded for analysis. Morphometric data were summarized using descriptive statistics and expressed as Mean \pm Standard Error of the Mean (SEM). Comparative evaluation of the measured parameters was performed descriptively to characterize morphological differences between the species. No inferential statistical tests were applied due to the small sample size.

RESULTS

Morphological Findings

Visual evaluation of the scapulae revealed marked morphological differences that are consistent with the contrasting functional demands of bipedal and quadrupedal locomotion.

Figure 1: Morphological Comparison of the Scapulae in Humans and Goats

A: Posterior view of the human scapula; B: Posterior view of the goat scapula; C: Anterior view of the human scapula; D: Anterior view of the goat scapula; E: Medial view of the human scapula; F: Medial view of the goat scapula; 1. Acromion process: Absent in goats; 2. Spine: Present in both species; 3. Suprascapular fossa: Present in both species; 4. Infraspinous fossa: Present in both species; 5. Neck of the scapula: Absent in humans; 6. Suprascapular notch: Absent in goats; 7. Coracoid process: Rudimentary in goats; 8. Glenoid cavity: Shallower in humans than in goats; 9. Subscapular fossa.

Processes and Spine: The human scapula featured a well-developed spine that terminated in a large, overhanging acromion process, as well as a robust, anteriorly projecting coracoid process. In contrast, the goat's scapular spine gradually faded distally, resulting in a markedly reduced acromion process. Furthermore, the goat's coracoid process was reduced to a rudimentary projection.

Scapular Neck: A distinct, elongated anatomical neck of the scapula was prominently visible in the goat, connecting the blade to the glenoid cavity. In humans, this neck was less distinct, with the glenoid situated tightly against the lateral angle of the body.

Suprascapular Notch: The superior border of the human scapular presented a suprascapular notch,

whereas no comparable notch was observed in the goat specimens examined.

Glenoid Cavity: Qualitative observations suggested that the human glenoid cavity was relatively shallower and more pyriform in shape than that of the goat, which appeared deeper and more rounded.

Fossae: Both species possessed defined supraspinous, infraspinous, and subscapular fossae, though their relative proportions differed noticeably due to the overall shape of the bones.

Morphometric Findings

Quantitative analysis highlighted marked differences, particularly regarding the bony projections that serve as muscular levers in humans.

Table 1: Morphometric Comparison of the Scapula in Humans and Goats

Parameter (cm)	Human (<i>Homo sapiens</i>) (Mean ± SEM)	Goat (<i>Capra hircus</i>) (Mean ± SEM)	Biomechanical Implication
Spine Length	12.8 ± 0.45	9.5 ± 0.40	Expanded trapezius/deltoid origin in humans.
Acromion Length	5.0 ± 0.18	0.0 ± 0.00	Crucial lever for human shoulder abduction.
Acromion Width	4.5 ± 0.30	0.0 ± 0.00	Massive lateral stabilization platform in humans.
Glenoid Fossa Radius	1.9 ± 0.11	1.5 ± 0.07	Shallower in humans for mobility; deeper in goats for stability.
Coracoid Process Length	4.3 ± 0.15	1.0 ± 0.03	Robust origin for human grasping musculature.
Coracoid Process Width	2.1 ± 0.12	0.5 ± 0.02	Wide base for human pectoralis minor/biceps attachment.

Note: Measurements in the goat represent the rudimentary coracoid/supraglenoid tubercle complex, as a true projecting coracoid process is absent.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal marked morphological and morphometric differences between the scapulae of humans (*Homo sapiens*) and domestic goats (*Capra hircus*). These differences are consistent with the contrasting locomotor behaviours and functional demands associated with habitual bipedalism and quadrupedalism. The observed variation supports established concepts in functional morphology, whereby skeletal structures are shaped by the biomechanical requirements of movement and posture, resulting in anatomical configurations adapted to specific locomotor strategies (Jacxsens *et al.*, 2020; Vermeulen *et al.*, 2023).

A key distinction observed in this study is the marked development of scapular processes in humans, particularly the acromion and coracoid processes. The expanded human acromion provides an extended lever arm for the deltoid muscle, enhancing humeral abduction and facilitating fine motor control of the upper limb. Similarly, the coracoid process serves as an important attachment site for stabilising musculature, including the short head of biceps brachii and pectoralis minor, thereby contributing to controlled mobility and joint stability (Standring, 2021; Moore *et al.*, 2022). These features reflect the functional demands of a freely mobile upper limb not primarily involved in weight-bearing.

In contrast, the scapula of the goat exhibits reduced prominence of these distal projections, consistent with its role in quadrupedal locomotion. In ungulates, the forelimb functions predominantly in weight transmission and cyclical locomotor loading, where stability and efficient force dissipation are prioritised over wide ranges of motion. As a result, scapular architecture tends to emphasize broad muscular attachment areas and robust load-bearing surfaces rather than enlarged lever-like processes (Dyce *et al.*, 2023; Makungu & Merere, 2017).

It is important to clarify that while the acromion is markedly reduced in goats, it is not entirely absent, and may present as a diminished or variably developed structure depending on species and anatomical interpretation. Similarly, the suprascapular notch is not absent in goats but is often transformed into a suprascapular foramen through ossification or

ligamentous bridging. These modifications are functionally relevant, as they maintain neurovascular passage while reinforcing the superior border of the scapula under mechanical stress.

Differences in glenoid morphology further highlight the functional trade-off between mobility and stability. The relatively shallow and more open glenoid cavity in humans permits a wide range of humeral motion, but this increased mobility is accompanied by reduced intrinsic osseous stability. Consequently, soft tissue structures, including the rotator cuff muscles and glenoid labrum, play a critical role in stabilising the shoulder joint during dynamic movement (Ladd *et al.*, 2021; Almajed *et al.*, 2022). In contrast, the deeper and more congruent glenoid morphology observed in goats contributes to enhanced joint stability, consistent with the mechanical demands of repetitive axial loading during locomotion.

From a broader evolutionary perspective, scapular positioning and orientation also reflect functional adaptation to locomotor strategy. In humans, the dorsally positioned scapula is associated with the decoupling of the upper limb from locomotor function, enabling increased freedom of movement and diversified manipulation (Laudicina & Cartmill, 2023). In quadrupedal mammals, the scapula is oriented to facilitate efficient stride mechanics and energy transfer through the forelimb, supporting sustained terrestrial locomotion.

Limitations

Several limitations are acknowledged. The sample size was relatively small, consisting of only five scapulae from each species, which may limit the generalisability of the findings. Furthermore, the study relied exclusively on osteological observations and morphometric measurements and did not incorporate biomechanical analyses, muscle architecture assessments, or kinematic investigations. Consequently, direct conclusions regarding locomotor efficiency, muscular leverage, or joint stability cannot be drawn from the present data alone. Future studies integrating osteological, biomechanical, and functional approaches would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between scapular morphology and locomotor adaptation.

Overall, the observed morphological and morphometric differences between human and goat scapulae are consistent with established models of functional adaptation in mammalian shoulder girdles. Rather than representing isolated anatomical variation, these differences reflect integrated biomechanical responses to contrasting demands of manipulation versus weight-bearing locomotion (Vermeulen et al., 2023; Jacxsens et al., 2020).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that human and non-primate mammalian scapulae represent distinct morphological solutions to differing biomechanical demands. In humans, the scapula is adapted for enhanced upper-limb mobility and functional versatility, reflected in features associated with muscular leverage and broad ranges of motion. In contrast, quadrupedal mammals exhibit scapular configurations that prioritise structural stability and locomotor efficiency under repetitive weight-bearing conditions. These differences suggest that scapular morphology is closely associated with locomotor behaviour and functional demand, reflecting long-term evolutionary adaptations of the shoulder girdle to distinct mechanical environments.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Odubela O.O. conceptualized and designed the study. All other authors participated in data collection and analysis, and the drafting and subsequent revision of the manuscript for publication.

